

Intelligent Urban Traffic Management via Semantic Interoperability across Multiple Heterogeneous Mobility Data Sources

Mario Scrocca¹, Marco Grassi¹, Marco Comerio¹,
Valentina Anita Carriero¹, Tiago Delgado Dias²,
Ana Vieira Da Silva², Irene Celino¹

¹ Cefriel – Milano, Italy

² A-to-Be – Lisbon, Portugal

TANGENT Solution – objective and data requirements

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TANGENT Solution – objective and data requirements

Accessing static and (quasi) real-time data to empower a set of applications for traffic managers

Collecting large-scale historical data for training of machine learning models to support traffic prediction

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Data Challenges – Sharing and Interoperability

1. **Locate:** *which data is available and where?*
2. **Access:** *how to obtain the data needed?*
3. **Harmonise:** *how to convert data according to a specific data model?*
4. **Integrate:** *how to ensure different data sources can be merged?*
5. **Extract:** *how to consume harmonized and integrated data?*

Data Harmonisation and Fusion Solution

- Four main components:
 1. **Data Catalogue**: a digital platform enabling data-sharing through uniform descriptions of data sources
 2. **Reference Conceptual Model**: a reference ontology for the transportation-related data handled by the catalogue
 3. **Semantic Harmonisation and Fusion Pipelines**: to fulfil the integration requirements associated with the data sources
 4. **Data API**: a uniform mechanism to access data sources collected and harmonized by downstream applications

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Data Harmonisation and Fusion Solution

1. Data Catalogue

The TANGENT Data Catalogue is a **digital platform** supporting the sharing, findability, and accessibility of distributed data sources

- Main features:
 - **Navigation/browsing of data sources** through a web interface
 - Description of data sources adopting the **TANGENT Metadata Profile**
 - **Searching/Filtering of data sources** according to specific metadata fields
 - Implementation of the **TANGENT Data-sharing Governance**

1. Data Catalogue

TANGENT HOME CATALOGUE WORKSPACE ADMIN

TANGENT Data Catalogue

The TANGENT Data Catalogue is a digital platform describing uniformly all the relevant data sources collected for the TANGENT case studies according to the TangentDCAT-AP metadata specification, and implementing governance mechanisms according to the TANGENT Data-Sharing Governance model.

Case study

Latest

Influencing Planned Events

Rennes Métropole

List Of Relevant Influencing Planned Events For Rennes

GeoJSON Polygon Of The TANGENT RENNES Case Study Area

Rennes Métropole

GeoJSON Polygon Of The TANGENT RENNES Case Study Area

Traffic Count Points

Rennes Métropole

GeoCoordinates For Relevant Sensor

Historical Planned Roadwork

Rennes Métropole

Delineation Of Roadworks Generating Disruptions To Traffic Over The Next 30 Days Including The Current Day

Historical Road Traffic Data

Rennes Métropole

Historical Traffic Data From Stations In PC Control

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- Historical Traffic Data For Stations In PC Control**

4 European Cities
145 Data Sources
3 Governance Roles
(Data Publisher, Data Management Board, Data User)
2 Governance Processes
(Data Sharing, Data Usage)
43 business stakeholder
who positively evaluated it

2. Reference Conceptual Model

- Reference conceptual model for the harmonisation of data sources
- Published online at <https://knowledge.c-innovationhub.com/tangent/schema>
- 10 ontological modules defined to cover the Data Requirements

language [en](#)

TANGENT Reference Conceptual Model

This version:
<https://knowledge.c-innovationhub.com/tangent/schema/1.0.0>

Revision:
1.0.0

Authors:
 Mario Scrocca (Cefriel)
 Valentina Carriero (Cefriel)

Contributors:
 Andrea Fiano (Cefriel)
 Gianluca Gizzi (Cefriel)
 Marco Comerio (Cefriel)
 Marco Grassi (Cefriel)

Publisher:
Cefriel

Funding:
<https://doi.org/10.3030/955273>

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Cite as:
 Mario Scrocca (Cefriel), Valentina Carriero (Cefriel), TANGENT Reference Conceptual Model. Revision: 1.0.0. Retrieved from: <https://knowledge.c-innovationhub.com/tangent/schema/1.0.0>
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Abstract

TANGENT ontology for the TANGENT Reference Conceptual Model.

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- 3. [Cross-reference for TANGENT Reference Conceptual Model classes, object properties and data properties](#)
 - 3.1. [Object Properties](#)

Module	Data Requirements
Road Transport Network	Road Transport Network (roads, limited access zones, etc)
Road Equipment	Road Equipment Position
Road Traffic Data	Road Traffic Measurements (traffic occupancy, speed, flow) Floating Vehicle Data (GPS, mobile, etc)
Road Travel Times	Road Travel Times (external services, statistics, etc.)
Events	Road Transport Network Events (planned) Road Transport Network Incidents (unplanned) Influencing Planned Events (sports, entertainment, etc) Weather Events
Weather Data	Forecasted Weather Data Weather Data (measurements, e.g., temperature, humidity, etc.)
Stop Points	Public Transport Network
Schedules	Public Transport Schedules and Lines
Situation Exchange	Public Transport Network Events (planned) Public Transport Network Incidents (unplanned)
Vehicle Monitoring	Floating PT Vehicle Data Public Transport Delays

2. Reference Conceptual Model

- Based on **standards recommended by EU Delegated Regulations**
- Reusing **existing ontologies** for the transportation domain

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10 ontology modules
6 reused ontologies
(2 composed by 7 sub-modules)
371 ad hoc definitions
(classes, object properties, datatype properties and named individuals)

3. Semantic Harmonisation and Fusion

- Any-to-one mapping approach:
 - Definition of mappings to represent the information contained in each data source using the TANGENT reference conceptual model
 - Defining mappings to extract information from the TANGENT reference conceptual model and represent them according to target data formats
- Data transformation pipelines, one for each data source
 - Implemented using the *Apache Camel* augmented with the data mapping capabilities from the **Chimera** software (<https://github.com/cefriel/chimera>)

Cf. M. Grassi et al. "Composable Semantic Data Transformation Pipelines with Chimera", In Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Knowledge Graph Construction (KGCW 2023)

3. Semantic Harmonisation and Fusion

TANGENT
Downstream
applications
(consuming
harmonised and
integrated data)

Both mapping blocks are implemented with the **Mapping Template Component** of the Chimera framework (<https://github.com/cefriel/mapping-template>)

Cf. M. Scrocca et al. "Not Everybody Speaks RDF: Knowledge Conversion between Different Data Representations", in Proceedings of 5th International Workshop on Knowledge Graph Construction (KGCW 2024).

4. Data API

- **Uniform access to data sources** handling authentication and data filtering details
- **Harmonized data flows** for the TANGENT dashboard and intelligent services for traffic management
- **Minimal impact** on pre-existing downstream applications

3.+4. Semantic Harmonisation and Fusion + Data API

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Collection of historical data for traffic prediction training

- Semantic Harmonisation and Fusion pipelines are defined to:
 - retrieve data from a data source
 - harmonise and aggregate data over time
- Data is harmonised and stored as CSV
- Uploaded to the TANGENT Data Catalogue and made available through the Data API

Data Source Identifier	Temporal Aggregation	Temporal Granularity	Aggregation Granularity	Harmonization format	Time Coverage
REN_BUST_10	yes	1 minute	1 day	CSV	April 2023 to October 2023
REN_BUST_11	yes	1 minute	1 day	CSV	April 2023 to October 2023
REN_METR_04	yes	1 minute	1 month	CSV	April 2023 to October 2023
REN_TRAF_12	yes	3 minutes	1 day	CSV	April 2023 to October 2023
REN_TRAF_14	yes	1 day	1 day	CSV	April 2023 to October 2023
REN_TRAF_15	yes	1 day	1 day	CSV	April 2023 to October 2023
TFGM_BUST_04	yes	10 sec	1 day	CSV	April 2023 to October 2023
TFGM_TRAM_02	yes	10 sec	1 day	CSV	April 2023 to October 2023

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REN_TRAF_12	yes	3 minutes	1 day	CSV	April 2023 to October 2023
REN_TRAF_14	yes	1 day	1 day		
REN_TRAF_15	yes	1 day	1 day		
TFGM_BUST_04	yes	10 sec	1 day		
TFGM_TRAM_02	yes	10 sec	1 day		

8 Historical Datasets
6 Months Collection
92GB Compressed Data
Enormous reduction of data scientist effort

Conclusions

- **Significance evaluation** of the proposed solution:
 - **Facilitate the findability of heterogeneous data sources** through the Data Catalogue through the collection of structured metadata in a common machine-readable format
 - **Remove the need for point-to-point integration** between different components through the Semantic Harmonisation and Fusion Pipelines and the Data API
- **Impact and uptake evaluation** of the proposed solution:
 - **Interoperability**: the reference conceptual model is adopted (and can possibly be extended) to foster interoperability of different solutions for traffic management
 - **Reusability**: the technological solutions developed for traffic management can be easily configured and adapted to any other domain or market, bringing the same interoperability advantages

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Thank you!

Presenter: Irene Celino irene.celino@cefriel.com

Main contact: Mario Scrocca mario.scrocca@cefriel.com

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No 955273

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